

Demilitarization in the Eastern Aegean Islands: A Historical Perspective

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Summary

This article examines the historical evolution of the demilitarization regime of the Eastern Aegean Islands from 1912 to the Montreux Convention of 1936. It evaluates the origins, legal foundations, and geopolitical motives behind Turkish claims, the 1914 Decision of the Six Powers, and the final regime established in Lausanne.

Keywords: Aegean Sea; Eastern Aegean Islands; Demilitarization; Lausanne Treaty; Article 13; Six Powers Decision; Montreux Convention; Greek–Turkish relations.

The issue of the demilitarization of the Aegean islands was first brought up by Turkey to the UN Security Council in 1976. In a letter dated 13 August 1976, the Turkish Permanent Representative, İlder Türkmen, informed the Secretary-General of the alleged “Greek Violations in the Aegean.” Türkmen argued that “the security of the Anatolian peninsula is much dependent on a great number of islands encircling it in the Aegean with very close geographic proximity,” claiming that the peculiar geographical configuration required reconciling sovereignty with the security of Anatolia.

Türkmen was referring to the change in the status quo in 1912, when during the Italo-Turkish War (1911–1912) Italy occupied the Dodecanese Islands, and during the First Balkan War Greece liberated the Eastern Aegean Islands. According to his interpretation, this change of circumstances led to the demilitarization of the Aegean Islands to safeguard the security of the Anatolian coast.

Turkey often invokes the so-called “Decision of the Six Powers” of 1914 to demand total demilitarization of all Eastern Aegean Islands. The Concert of Europe – that is, the six Great Powers (Great Britain, France, Russia, Germany, Austria-Hungary, and Italy) before the outbreak of the First World War – acted collectively on matters concerning the Aegean.

They did indeed request in 1912 that the islands liberated by Greece during the First Balkan War be neutralized under the collective guarantee of the Powers. This idea had been formulated earlier by the British Admiralty, whose principal concern was to ensure that no Great Power—Italy above all—would be able to establish a naval base in the Aegean.

The alleged connection between sovereignty and demilitarization can be debunked by referring to the historical facts. The Ottoman Empire unconditionally accepted the principle that the fate of all the islands would be determined by the Six Powers. As the Foreign Office noted in December 1913, the Turkish government accepted the principle unconditionally through three diplomatic acts:

- Article 5 of the Treaty of London (May 30, 1913)
- Article 15 of the Treaty of Athens (November 1, 1913)
- The Turkish Note of April 1, 1913, responding to the joint *démarche* of the Six Powers

In early 1914, the conflicting interests of the Powers—particularly Germany’s refusal to apply coercive pressure on Turkey—prevented the enforcement of the Six Powers’ decision. This forced Prime Minister Eleftherios Venizelos to resist German proposals for the demilitarization of all Eastern Aegean Islands without clear guarantees of peaceful Greek possession. Turkey’s reply merely “acknowledged receipt” of the decision rather than accepting it formally. Had Turkey rejected it outright, the Powers would have been compelled to enforce it—something Berlin and Paris discouraged.

Immediately after the Six Powers’ Decision in February 1914, Greece was pushed into bilateral negotiations with Turkey. Venizelos was initially conciliatory because Turkey held decisive leverage: the threat of expelling two million Greeks from Asia Minor, Thrace, and Constantinople. After the Ottoman-German alliance in August 1914, the Turks demanded the return of Chios, Lesbos, Samos, and Lemnos. In September 1914 the British declared that they considered the Turkish fleet an annex of the German fleet and would sink it if it left the Straits. With the Royal Navy effectively guaranteeing Greek sovereignty, Venizelos ended bilateral negotiations.

Venizelos had also prepared a draft royal decree for the annexation of the Eastern Aegean Islands, which would amount to a unilateral enforcement of the Six Powers’ decision. By September 1914 he informed the Ottoman ambassador that Greece would not act unilaterally, as he refused both to return Imbros, Tenedos, and Kastellorizo to Turkey and to accept demilitarization obligations. Instead, he pursued alignment with the Entente, hoping for a better post-war settlement.

During the Lausanne Conference (1922–1923), demilitarization was explicitly discussed only for eight islands: Chios, Lesbos, Samos, and Ikaria (Article 13 of the Lausanne Treaty), and Samothrace, Lemnos, Imbros, Tenedos, and Rabbit Islands (Article 4 of the Lausanne Straits Convention). Article 4 required the demilitarization of both shores of the Dardanelles and Bosphorus and nearby islands. The 1923 Straits Convention was completely superseded in 1936 by the Montreux Convention, which lifted all demilitarization obligations for the Straits region, including Samothrace and Lemnos.

Article 13 of Lausanne imposed a modified form of demilitarization on Chios, Lesbos, Samos, and Ikaria, allowing Greece to maintain gendarmerie, limited forces, and unrestricted aviation facilities. İsmet İnönü described the demilitarization as “almost illusory,” reflecting its limited scope. Turkey initially opposed the article but ultimately ratified Lausanne in full on July 24, 1923.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although Greece suffered a military defeat in Asia Minor, it remained on the winning side of World War I alongside the Allied Powers—Great Britain, France, the United States, and their partners. Turkey, as the successor state to the defeated Ottoman Empire, entered the Lausanne Conference from a very different diplomatic position. For this reason, the Allied Powers consistently rejected Turkish proposals for the total demilitarization of the Eastern Aegean Islands.

The only demilitarization provisions ultimately adopted were those contained in Article 13 of the Lausanne Treaty, and they applied exclusively to four islands: Lesbos, Chios, Samos, and Ikaria. Even in this limited form, the restrictions were significantly moderated; Greece retained the right to maintain gendarmerie, limited forces, and full aviation facilities. This is why İsmet İnönü, head of the Turkish delegation, characterized the resulting arrangement as “almost illusory”, acknowledging that it did not constitute substantive demilitarization in practice.

Therefore, with respect to the Eastern Aegean, Greece today is bound only by the narrow and explicitly defined obligations of Article 13—and only for the four islands named in that article. No additional or broader demilitarization regime exists in treaty law, nor was one ever accepted by the Allied Powers during the Lausanne negotiations.